

Real-Time Crowd Counting and Density Estimation Using OpenCV and Deep Learning

Sushma R
PG Student
Dept. of CSE

Channabasaveshwara Institute of Technology
Gubbi , Karnataka, India– 572216

Ranjitha S Y
Assistant Professor,
Dept. of CSE

Channabasaveshwara Institute of Technology
Gubbi , Karnataka, India– 572216

Dr. Manoj Kumar D P
Associate Professor,
Dept. of CSE

Kalpataru Institute of Technology Tiptur,
Karnataka, India– 572201

Dr .Suhas K C
Associate Professor,
Dept. of CSE

Channabasaveshwara Institute of Technology
Gubbi , Karnataka, India– 572216

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Abstract -Public spaces are frequented by large crowds of people on occasion. To prevent public disasters such as stampedes, confusion, social distancing, pandemic danger, etc., crowd control is essential under these circumstances. In order to reduce the pandemic's rate and stop it from spreading, it became necessary to control these gatherings. This would be a clever and effective system. With a comparatively straightforward and user-friendly interface, the framework is built on computer vision. The sensor, administration, and interface layers make up the three levels that make up the framework. The sensor layer is in charge of collecting information about how many individuals are entering a room. Verifying whether or not the restricted count of a specific room has been reached is the responsibility of the management phase. The interface layer is in charge of using a buzzer to notify the security personnel that the restricted number of people inside the room has been reached and that no additional civilians are permitted. This arrangement works well in enclosed areas such as rooms, shops, conference rooms, elevators, etc. We use Python to execute OpenCV ideas in a vast area, measuring the distance between each person and alerting them if they go beyond the predetermined distance inside the crowd. The pixel position of a specific person in the scene is used to determine the estimated distance between two people. To produce the outcome, we employ image processing. Should any of the persons surpass the limit, a red alert will appear; if not, they can proceed.

Keywords – OpenCV, Crowd Detection, People counting, Image processing, Real-time detection, Background Subtraction, Motion Detection, Tracking, Feature Extraction, Video Analysis, Security Systems, Smart Cities, Crowd Management

I.INTRODUCTION

At large-scale events like concerts, festivals, sports, games, and entertainment, crowding is a frequent occurrence. Analysing crowd behaviour is one of the most fascinating and active areas of computer vision research. A crowd is a collection of individuals in one place. The crowd in a temple will be different from the throng in a retail centre. Crowds vary depending on the circumstances. A

crowd is a collection of people who are in the same physical location. The growing human population of today tends to make public spaces more crowded [3].

Consequently, it is necessary to examine the surveillance system using multiple closed circuit television the crowd is observed via television. Not all of the cameras can be seen at once with the human eye. Therefore, it is necessary to employ an automated method to keep a close eye on the audience for an extended length of time. A significant amount of data needs to be processed, real-time detection, occlusions, and the simultaneous occurrence of several events are challenging issues in automatically detecting the desired events. The suggested approach can be used with a limited collection of objects. With the ability to transmit data over a network without requiring human intervention, the Internet of Things is a potent industrial system of wireless and radio-frequency identification devices [1]. For the purpose of public safety, crowd behavior analysis utilizing surveillance footage is crucial since it makes it possible to identify potentially dangerous groups and track their movements.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper 1: "Efficient wireless sensor network rings overlay for crowd management in Arafat area of Makkah."

Author: S. Hashish, and M. Ahmed

Year of publication: 2015

Explanation: Sensor-enabled smartphones are being used by researchers as tags for extensive human sensing. Future tracking of more people will be possible without them having to provide a tag thanks to the growing use of smartphones. Certain location monitoring systems that rely on smartphones necessitate the installation of an application on the client's smartphone. The loaded program uses the smartphone's GPS sensor to determine its location, and it uses an Internet connection to continuously update the location to a distant server. Nonetheless, it is uncommon for users

in densely populated areas and isolated places to always have an Internet connection. The proliferation of operating systems and versions for smartphones poses a challenge to the creation and dissemination of applications. Crowd sensing becomes an air pollution monitoring solution when it adopts the Smart City paradigm. The gathered information is routinely sent to a central server for processing and storing.

Paper2: "IoT-based Framework for Crowd Management", Computer Science Department, Faculty of Computers and Informatics Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt, IEEE International Conference on IoT.

Authors: Marwa F. Mohamed, Abd El Rahman Shabayek, Mahmoud ElGayyar

Year of publication: 2018

Explanation: With the ability to transport data over a network without requiring human intervention, the Internet of Things is a potent industrial system for radio-frequency identification and wireless devices. The three main layers of the Internet of Things are the sensing layer, which uses hardware already in place to collect data from the real world, the network layer, which transfers the data across wired or wireless networks, and the application layer, which facilitates two-way communication between users and systems. IoT applications are expanding quickly across many industries. Detecting and controlling crowds with standard sensors is a difficult task. The process of crowd management involves multiple stages, such as gathering crowd data through sensor levels, transmitting data through network layers, analyzing data to make decisions, and implementing crowd control measures through application layers. It is feasible to collect data on visitor crowds and identify places that are overloaded by using various sensor devices. After that, this data is sent to the management layer, where the administrator has the authority to determine which doors and roads to close. To guide the flow of people, a smart service that can suggest which doors to open or close must be installed in the management layer. The administrators then determine whether or not to make this information publicly available. The application has an intuitive UI and multiple languages to improve user end application usability.

Paper 3: "Enhancing crowd monitoring system functionality through data fusion: Estimating flow rate from Wi-Fi traces and automated counting system data."

Authors: D .C. Duives, T. van Oijen and S. P. Hoogendoorn

Year of publication: 2020

Explanation: Smart city-oriented intelligent applications have grown in importance as a service to humankind with the advancement of sensor, communication, and big data science. The standard of living for people has enhanced with better infrastructure and clever applications, such smart building and smart home

furnishings. Urban commercial zones are growing in number and prosperity, and as a result, some individuals prefer to shop and find pleasure there. These sizable central business districts, which are also the most vibrant economically, have come to symbolize the city. In addition to individuals. It is possible to assess the level of crowd gathering for precise and efficient management and planning at a monitored location by calculating the number of individual. Customer audience Closed-circuit television monitoring is the most widely used type of vision-based monitoring technology, which is the foundation of monitoring systems. Stated differently, the signal can be sent from the data source to a designated broadcast device that is connected to the source in advance. A type of information fusion technology called data fusion links, correlates, and combines data from various sensors to provide more precise and rapid decision support. Data fusion provides practical and highly efficient support for deep fusion and mining enormous multi-source data in heterogeneous networks, from low-level data collecting to high-level services.

Paper 4: "The Crowd Congestion Level a New Measure for Risk Assessment in Video Based Crowd Monitoring", International Journal of Information Technology and Decision Making 3(4):2353- 2361

Author: Sebastian Bek and Eduardo Monari

Year of publication: 2015

Explanation: Additional types of crowd counting in video sensing include line of interest counting, which counts the number of people that cross a detecting line during an instance, and region of interest counting, which calculates the total number of persons that region at an instance. Using feature tracking approaches, the line of interest counts can be developed either by counting crowd densities from a temporal frame of the video or by computing trajectories and clubbing them into object tracks. If too many people are seen in one specific geographic area of a crowded scene, then those individuals should be considered endangered. Nevertheless, absolute density can be exceedingly challenging to obtain from crowd footage, and density by itself is insufficient as a defining figure. We found that in situations when there is a high population density, as long as people are still able to move freely and easily through the crowd, the situation can be considered non-critical. Consequently, we think that while assessing risk, data on the flow dynamics should be used. Our method is predicated on the idea that if a localized area of the crowd experiences a dramatic decrease in motion dynamics while the density is steadily rising over time, then that area may be crucial.

Paper5: "An IoT System for Social Distancing and Emergency Management in Smart Cities Using Multi-Sensor Data", In 2017 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Informatics, Communication and Energy Systems.

Author: Rosario Fedele and Massimo Merenda

Year of publication: 2017

Explanation: Because there is so much information on the internet, recommender systems technology seeks to limit consumer over choice. These systems make advantage of data acquired from a small number of encounters with its user, in order to generate a personalized list of products that can pique their interest and improve their overall user experience. The application of machine learning and deep learning methods for information retrieval could enhance recommender systems even more. If information retrieval algorithms from machine learning and deep learning were applied, recommender systems may be significantly enhanced. A mobile Internet of Things recommender system for users who need to locate Park-and-Ride infrastructures in order to transition from a private to a public transportation mode is one of the noteworthy applications of recommender systems in smart cities. Another is an autonomous situation-aware evacuation route recommender architecture that is optimized in real time to obtain smart buildings, reuse data generated by multiple IoT applications, and modify the services offered by the single IoT system in order to enhance the user experience.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. ARCHITECTURE:

Fig1.1-Architecture Diagram

B. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION:

1) GIT&GITHUB [3.8.0]

A distributed version control system called GIT records changes made to any group of digital assets. It is widely employed to organize the work of programmers who are working together to develop the source code for software. Speed, data integrity, and support for dispersed, non-linear activities are among its objectives.

GitHub is a website hosting service for Git-based version control and software development. It offers each project access control, bug tracking, software feature requests, task management, continuous integration, and wikis in addition to Git's distributed version control.

2) PYTHON COMPILER [3.6]

In addition to faster asynchronous I/O, Python 3.6 enhances script compilation, trash collection, and the addition of new classes for handling data. The most widely used version of the language, Python 3.6, aims to make difficult tasks easy.

3) PYCHARM OPEN-SOURCE IDE [2023.1]

An Integrated Development Environment (IDE) like PyCharm is a must have for Python developers. Together, these technologies produce a setting that is beneficial for Python, web, data science development, and machine learning operation.

C. INSTALLING PACKAGES:

- Here we use Python compiler version 3.8.0 and OpenCV version 4.2.0. +. NumPy and SciPy is also used for some calculations required for this experiment.
- *The fundamental* Python library or complex mathematical computing is called NumPy. A multidimensional array object and a number of derivative objects are provided by this Python package (such as masked arrays and matrices).
- SciPy is a library for scientific computation Python is an open-source, BSD-licensed library for computing applications in mathematics, science, and engineering.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Input design

The footage from a real-time CCTV camera installed in any public space where it's necessary to keep an eye on crowds and encourage people to disperse rather than congregate serves as the module's input design a single region.

Output design

The output design for this module is shown on the same monitor that receives the video feed from the CCTV camera as input. It shows the quantity of infractions by crowds on the monitor screen and also distinguishes. The individuals in the scenario are displayed in a yellow rectangular box for those who have violated the crowd, and those who are not violating the crowd are enclosed in a blue rectangular box.

Testing

Software testing is a technique used to verify that a software product is error-free and that it satisfies specified requirements. It entails using a system or piece of software. Components that assess one or more attributes of interest using automated or manual tools. Software testing's goal is to find mistakes, holes, or requirements that are lacking compared to the requirements as written.

Types of testing:

Unit testing

Major components that are crucial to the unit testing process include the performance of the suggested model in our IoT design is checked and verified, followed by the sensors where it functions, the battery to power up the Arduino and sensor, and finally the components related to the software working of the model are checked and verified. The camera used is tested for its functionality and verified, and in order to run the Python code for crowd detection, we have used Python. Python is executed in the local machine to which the CCTV camera is connected, so its setup is verified.

Functional testing

During this step, the components' intended functionality is tested to see if they deliver the desired outcome. The sensor and Arduino are tested to see if they accurately count individuals and sound a warning when the restricted count is achieved. The Python code is run on the CCTV camera's input video to see if it can recognize crowds in public spaces and tell them apart using rectangular boxes that are green and blue.

Integration testing

In this testing, the components' integrated functionality is examined and confirmed. The Arduino, sensor, and battery are checked to see if they can cooperate with one another and become attached. The camera as well as the code is checked in tandem to determine whether the camera image is utilized appropriately for crowd detection.

White box testing

The right route must be specified in order for the CCTV camera in public spaces and shopping centers to identify crowds. This will allow us to verify if the data is present in the requested folder. Components of it Presume that in order to get better outcomes, you should complete the tasks that the program is supposed to perform.

Black box testing

Developers are not needed for this testing because the person conducting it lacks development experience and only needs to verify that the inputs are producing the desired results. Give some for this test. Use the program's ability to recognize and warn about crowds in the minutes-long recorded footage as input.

Testing Strategy

Our approach to testing our suggested model was to first ensure that the Arduino, sensor, and buzzer combination was working to provide the right output on the LCD screen by testing the components in a contained space and also the buzzer sounding at the appropriate moment. Next, we looked for real-time CCTV cameras installed in public areas. Since we didn't have access to any, we looked at our proposed model, which had previously recorded video in the format of an mp4, and it correctly monitored and displayed the crowd violated area. Finally, we started with the computer

specifications before installing our model in the system and installing any supporting libraries needed for our model to monitor crowds.

FLOW CHART:

Fig2.1-Crowd Detector

This flow chart depicts a social distancing analyzer model that processes video frames to detect people, transform the view to a top-down perspective, measure the distance between individuals, mark those too close with red boxes, those sufficiently distanced with green boxes, display the results, and repeat until the end of the video.

V. RESULTS

This project typically is a less cost effective and more economically benefit able to the organization which builds this project and also to the society considering the current undergoing pandemic situation.

The analysis of this project ensures in helping government organizations and other NGO to determine their viability, cost, and benefits associated with this project before financial resources are allocated to help the needy.

From a technical point of view we can assure that the idea can be converted to working system with the already ready available technologies and hardware systems available to the organization. It

also serves as an independent project assessment and enhances project credibility helping decision makers determine the positive economic benefits to the organization that the proposed project will provide.

Social impact analysis of our project greatly reduces the overall risks of being inhuman to the surrounding and its people and also helps to reduce resistance, strengthens support of the people towards the government organization, and allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the costs and benefits of the project.

Output-1:

Output-2:

Fig3.2–Crowd Detector

VI. CONCLUSION

We've spoken about the framework for crowd management, which distributes visitors throughout a busy space. The purpose of the sensors layer is to monitor and record visitor behavior and demographic data. The goal of the management layer is to after

administrative approval, examine the gathered data and extract the necessary visitor information. By informing administrators and guests about the number of people in a certain location and in an employ computer vision with Python to estimate the distance between each person and consider them as a crowd violator if they do not respect the distance between each other. The suggested framework will assist administrators in efficiently managing and allocating guests, saving them time and effort.

Additionally, the proposed framework will be useable by everyone, regardless of age or gender, if they can turn on or off an electric circuit to operate our proposed model in a closed environment, or if they know how to operate a computer in the case of the open space model. When working in a large space, we employ computer vision with Python to estimate the distance between each person and consider them as a crowd violator if they don't respect the distance between each other. The suggested framework will assist administrators in efficiently managing and allocating guests, saving them time and effort.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] S. Hashish, and M. Ahmed (2015). "Efficient wireless sensor network rings overlay for crowd management in Arafat area of Makkah." In 2015 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Informatics, Communication and Energy Systems, pp. 1-6.
- [2] D. C. Duives, T. van Oijen, and S. P. Hoogendoorn (2020), "Enhancing crowd monitoring system functionality through data fusion: Estimating flow rate from Wi-Fi traces and automated counting system data," IEEE Sensors, vol. 20, no. 21, p. 6032.
- [3] Marwa F. Mohamed, Abd El Rahman Shabayek, Mahmoud ElGayyar (2018), "IoT-based Framework for Crowd Management", Computer Science Department, Faculty of Computes and Informatics Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt, IEEE International Conference on IoT.
- [4] Jianjie Yang, Jin Li, Ye He, "Crowd Density and Counting Estimation Based on Image Textural Feature", JOURNAL OF MULTIMEDIA, VOL. 9, NO. 10, OCTOBER 2014.
- [5] Aditya vora, Vinay chilaka, "fchd: fast and accurate head detection in crowded scenes", arxiv:1809.08766v3 [cs.cv] 5 may 2019
- [6] Sheng-Fuu Lin, Member, IEEE, Jaw-Yeh Chen, and Hung-Xin Chao, "Estimation of Number of People in Crowded Scenes Using Perspective Transformation" IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics—part a: systems and humans, vol. 31, no. 6, November 2001.
- [7] Mikel Rodriguez, Ivan Laptev, Josef Sivic, Jean-Yves Audibert, "Density-aware person detection and tracking in crowds. Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (2011)".